

The Vocabulary of Mark's Gospel, the LXX and the Greek of its time

Alfredo Delgado Gómez
La Salle University, Madrid

Abstract

This article compares Mark's vocabulary with Septuagint's vocabulary and with the Greek of its time. The relationship of the vocabulary of other works close to Mark's Gospel is also contrasted with the LXX. These works have been chosen because of their Jewish register (Paul, Josephus, Philo, *Joseph and Aseneth*), its closeness in terms of literary genre (*Life of Apollonius*, *Evagoras*, *Agesilaus*) or linguistic variety (Polibius, Epictetus) with Mark. Mark's vocabulary is also placed in his contemporary context to understand his semantic options. This analysis concludes that 90% of Mark's vocabulary is Septuagintal, and it could be reduced to 43 roots not appearing in LXX.

Keywords

Gospel of Mark, Septuagint, Koine Greek, intertextuality, Classical Greek.

Pre-print version

1 Introduction

There are several elements which connect Mark's Gospel with the books and the narrative of the LXX¹. First, idioms: "son of man" (Dan 7,13-14), "the abomination of desolation" (Dan 11,31), "son of David" (Ps 17,21), "corner stone" (Ps 118,22), "what do we have to do with you?" (Judg 11,12). Second, expressions not found in non-biblical Greek: καὶ ἐγένετο, καὶ εὐθύς, καθὼς γέγραπται, ἀποκριθεὶς εἶπεν, ἰδοὺ. Third, syntax, largely devoid of Atticist traits, is strongly influenced by the LXX as reflected in its paratactic style and the use of verbal periphrasis ἤρξατο + infinitive and ἦν + participle. There are cases of grammaticalization by the influence of the LXX in Mark in the communication verbs (εἶπεν, ἀποκριθεὶς), in the verbs of movement (ἐλθὼν, καταλιπὼν), in postural verbs, in certain conjunctions (ὅτι 102x; ἵνα 64x) and in adverbs (τότε 6x; εὐθύς 41x)². Fourth, literary style (paratactic) with a scarce use of particles³ (ἄρα 2x; μὲν δέ 3x; οὖν 3x, while οὖν appears 200x in John; δέ 152x while in Matthew 421x and in Luke 478x). In this sense Swete asserted that Mark "was intimately acquainted with the language of the Greek Bible"⁴. Fifth, worldview⁵ and world of the text, through which Mark aims to continue the narrative of God's action in aid of his people as it was written in the LXX books. Sixth, characters, such as Moses and Elijah (Mark 9,4), not to mention all the referred characters appearing in the narrative (Abraham, David, etc.). Seventh, quotations and allusions to the books of LXX⁶ including one explicit reference to Isaiah at the beginning of the Gospel, introduced by a stereotyped formula belonging to the LXX and reclaiming its authority: καθὼς γέγραπται ἐν τῷ Ἡσαΐα τῷ προφήτῃ (Mark 1,2; 2 Kings 14,6 LXX). Especially the concepts of style and intertextuality are persuasive in establishing the connection between the NT and the LXX. Imitation and allusion are the strategies through which Mark pays homage to the Septuagint as Holy Scripture⁷.

Given this close relationship between Mark's Gospel and the LXX books we could ask ourselves, what is the relationship between LXX and Mark's vocabularies? Was Mark's Gospel built with LXX words or its vocabulary does not reflect a specific relationship with the LXX? Furthermore, what is it the relationship of Mark's vocabulary with the Greek of its time? Which are Mark's vocabulary influences: Classical words or new words coming from Koine Greek?

¹ The LXX is a set of books, written from III BCE to I BCE. Most of them are the Greek translation of the original Hebrew (and Aramaic) books of the OT, while several of them were composed in Greek.

² S.-I. LEE, *Jesus and Gospel traditions in bilingual context. A study in the interdirectionality of language* (BZNW 186; Berlin 2012) 252-281.

³ Mark has written in a coherent low style but he is capable of a superior style, for example, in the Jesus' direct speeches the number of particles increases. J. A. L. LEE, «Some Features of the Speech of Jesus in Mark's Gospel», *Novum Testamentum* 27:1 (1985) 1-26.

⁴ H. B. SWETE, *The Gospel according to St. Mark* (London 1898) lxxx.

⁵ M. NEL, «The Gospel of Mark in Light of its Apocalyptic Worldview», *Journal of Early Christian History* 4:1 (2014) 135-148.

⁶ The Gospel has 69 quotations from the books of the LXX. Half of these citations are from the Prophets, namely 37 from Isaiah and 9 from Daniel. There are 19 from the Pentateuch and 12 from the Psalms. R. E. WATTS, «Mark», *Commentary on the New Testament use of the Old Testament* (ed. G. K. BEALE – D. A. CARSON) (Grand Rapids, MI 2007) 111-250, here 111. In the Index of the NA²⁸ more than 350 references from the OT appear in Mark. There are references to every book of the LXX with the exception of 1 Chr, 3 Macc, Obad, Nah, Hab.

⁷ M. WEIGER, «Le Vocabulaire de la Septante dans le Nouveau Testament», *Die Sprache der Septuaginta/The Language of the Septuagint* (ed. E. BONS – J. JOOSTEN) (LXX.H 3; Gütersloh 2016) 440-450, here 450.

Mark's vocabulary has been studied previously, but it was done with the objectives of knowing its hypothetical preceding sources and identifying its specific theology⁸. No significant studies of the vocabulary of the NT and its relationship with the Septuagint or with Classical Greek have been produced since those that were published over 100 years ago⁹. These studies perpetuated several errors resulting from a scarcity of sources and tools. But with the discovery of new papyri and inscriptions and the publication of new dictionaries, as well as new digital tools, further study in these areas is now called for¹⁰. In fact, Edwin A. Judge asserted that over the fifty years between the publication of Moulton-Milligan's book and the first volume of the *NewDocs* (1976), the number of volumes with publications of documentary papyri was five times larger than in 1930¹¹. This situation deserves a new study of Mark's vocabulary.

Pre-print version

⁸ F. NEIRYNCK, *Duality in Mark*. Contributions to the study of the Markan redaction (BETL 31; Leuven²1988). E. J. PRYKE, *Redactional style in the Marcan Gospel*. A study of syntax and vocabulary as guides to redaction in Mark (Cambridge 1978). J. C. DOUDNA, *The Greek of the Gospel of Mark* (Philadelphia 1961). Head points out the difficulty of establishing a clear list of Markan words. P. M. HEAD, «Mark's Vocabulary: A Survey of Approaches and Material», *Estudios Bíblicos* 79:1 (2021) 78-108, here 83-95. My analysis of these lists reveals that only four words do not appear in the LXX: μαθητής, κράβατος, συζητέω and σταυρός (σταυρόω appears in LXX), and only μεθερμηνεύω is post-classical.

⁹ H. A. A. KENNEDY, *Sources of New Testament Greek*. The influence of the Septuagint on the vocabulary of the New Testament (Edinburgh 1895). T. K. ABBOTT, *Essays chiefly on the original texts of the Old and New Testaments* (London 1891). M. SILVA, «The Language of the Septuagint and the New Testament: Prolegomena», *Die Sprache der Septuaginta/The Language of the Septuagint* (ed. E. BONS – J. JOOSTEN) (LXX.H 3; Gütersloh 2016) 431-439.

¹⁰ Especially significant new dictionaries are F. MONTANARI, *The Brill Dictionary of Ancient Greek* (Boston, MA 2015) (GE) and T. MURAKA, *A Greek-English lexicon of the Septuagint* (Louvain²2009) (GELS).

¹¹ E. A. JUDGE, «Preface», *New documents illustrating early Christianity*. A review of the Greek inscriptions and papyri published in 1976 (ed. G. H. R. HORSLEY) (NewDocs 1; North Ryde, Australia 1971) iv-v, here v.

2 Aim and method

The objective of this article is to analyse the relationship of the vocabulary of Mark with the vocabulary of the Septuagint and to place Mark's vocabulary in the context of 1st century CE Greek, in order to conclude if Mark's vocabulary could reflect an implicit aim in connecting his story with the LXX. In order to achieve this, firstly Mark's vocabulary will be contrasted with LXX's vocabulary. Secondly, the relationship of the vocabulary of other contemporary works close to Mark's Gospel will be contrasted and compared with the LXX. These works have been chosen because of their Jewish register¹² (Paul, Josephus, Philo, *Joseph and Aseneth*) or because of its closeness in terms of literary genre¹³ (*Life of Apollonius*, *Evagoras*, *Agésilas*) or linguistic variety (Polybius, Epictetus) with Mark. Thirdly, Mark's vocabulary will be placed in its contemporary context to assess previous results and to understand his semantic influences. It must be pointed out that the linguistic study of the Gospel should be carried out by analysing its genre, linguistic variety, style, register, syntax and vocabulary¹⁴. In this article we focus on vocabulary.

The method of analysis of Mark's vocabulary adopted here is centered on the linguistic written forms (the symbols) and not on their meanings or senses, which would require a different approach¹⁵. This study is a corpus-based linguistics analysis of the vocabulary of the Gospel of Mark compared with three corpora: first, the corpus formed by the books of the LXX; second, texts written in Koine Greek (documentary and literary) and third, literary texts written in classical Greek before Aristotle.

This analysis has been carried out using the NA 28 Greek text of Mark's Gospel and Ralph's text of the LXX. The results have been verified using Morgenthaler's statistics¹⁶, which have been verified and corrected. Isocrates, Xenophon, Epictetus, Philostratus and Polybius' works in the Perseus and TLG's editions have been analysed after creating new modules for Bibleworks 10, and then compared to the biblical texts. The definitions and etymologies are derived from GE and have been verified in EGD¹⁷ and also in Chantraine¹⁸. The words and their attestations have been analysed using a number of dictionaries: GE, GI¹⁹, DGE²⁰, LSJ

¹² Register is a set of language items associated with social groups, specific occupations or institutions. R. WARDHAUGH, *An introduction to sociolinguistics* (West Sussex, UK 2010) 52. Register entails text and implies a relationship between text and context. D. BIBER – E. FINEGAN, *Sociolinguistic perspectives on register* (Oxford 1994) 7.

¹³ These works have been taken as "genre models" close to Mark by R. A. BURRIDGE, *What are the Gospels? A Comparison with Graeco-Roman Biography* (Grand Rapids, MI 2004).

¹⁴ A. DELGADO GÓMEZ, «Género y registro del evangelio de Marcos desde la perspectiva sociolingüística», *Estudios Agustinos* 53 (2018) 5-36.

¹⁵ M. JANSE, «The Greek of the New Testament», *A History of Ancient Greek. From the Beginnings to Late Antiquity* (ed. A. F. CHRISTIDIS) (Cambridge 2007) 646-653.

¹⁶ R. MORGENTHALER, *Statistik des Neutestamentlichen Wortschatzes* (Zürich 1958). Contrary to him, in this study only Mark 1.1–16.8 is taken into account.

¹⁷ R. S. P. BEEKES – L. V. BEEK, *Etymological Dictionary of Greek* (Leiden 2010). (EDG).

¹⁸ P. CHANTRAINE, *Dictionnaire étymologique de la langue grecque. Histoire des mots* (Paris 1999).

¹⁹ F. MONTANARI – D. MANETTI – I. GAROFALO, *Vocabolario della lingua greca. Greco-italiano* (Torino 2004).

²⁰ F. RODRÍGUEZ ADRADOS – J. A. BERENQUER, *Diccionario griego-español* (Madrid 2008) (DGL).

²¹, BDAG ²², MM ²³, Thayer ²⁴, Preisigke ²⁵, *NewDocs* ²⁶; Mauersberger²⁷ for Polybius and GELS and LEH for the LXX ²⁸. The attestation of the words in papyri and inscriptions have also been studied using a number of databases ²⁹.

Pre-print version

²¹ H. G. LIDDELL – R. SCOTT – H. S. JONES, *A Greek-English lexicon* (Oxford ⁹1996). (LSJ).

²² W. BAUER – W. F. ARNDT – F. W. DANKER, *A Greek-English lexicon of the New Testament and other early Christian literature* (Chicago ³2000).

²³ J. H. MOULTON – G. MILLIGAN, *The vocabulary of the Greek Testament*. Illustrated from the papyri and other non-literary sources (London 1929) (MM).

²⁴ J. H. THAYER – C. L. W. GRIMM – C. G. WILKE, *A Greek-English lexicon of the New Testament, being Grimm's Wilke's Clavis Novi Testamenti* (New York ²1889).

²⁵ F. PREISIGKE – E. KIESSLING – O. GRADENWITZ, *Wörterbuch der griechischen Papyrusurkunden* (Berlin 1925) and the next supplements.

²⁶ G. H. R. HORSLEY – S. R. LLEWELYN, *New documents illustrating early Christianity* (North Ryde, Australia 1981-2012). (*NewDocs*).

²⁷ A. MAUERSBERGER – C.-F. COLLATZ – H. HELMS, et al., *Polybios-Lexikon* (Berlin ²2000).

²⁸ J. LUST – E. EYNIKEL – K. HAUSPIE, et al., *A Greek-English lexicon of the Septuagint* (Berlin 2003).

²⁹ papyri.info, trismegistos.org, PHI Greek Inscriptions and D. HAGEDORN – K. MARESCH, *WörterListen aus den Registern von Publikationen griechischer und lateinischer dokumentarischer Papyri und Ostraka* (Heidelberg Uni 2018) (WL).

3 Vocabulary of Mark in the LXX

3.1 Words appearing in the LXX

Mark's Gospel consists of approximately 11,133 words related to 1,315 lemmas³⁰. After contrasting Mark's vocabulary with the LXX the outcome is that only 183 lemmas in the Gospel do not appear in the Septuagint, representing 10.23% of the total lemmas³¹. Excluding proper names³², place names, demonyms³³, and collectives³⁴, and two words with different transcription in the LXX³⁵, only 128 lemmas of the total lemmas do not appear in the LXX. These words are shown in Table 1, with their attestations and morphology³⁶.

There are only 12 lemmas used in Mark's Gospel which only appear in the LXX³⁷ and are not attested elsewhere³⁸. This confirms that the use of neologisms from the LXX in Mark is scarce. Seven of them are: ἀμὴν (14x), ἀναθεματίζω, οὐαί, πειρασμός, προσάββατον³⁹, σατανᾶς (6x), σκληροκαρδία. The remaining five words appear in Mark as part of explicit quotations from the LXX, e.g. τὸ βδέλυγμα τῆς ἐρημώσεως (Dan 12,11); ἔνταλμα (Isa 29,13); ὀλοκαύτωμα (Lev 14,31); προσευχή (Isa 56,7).

Mark shares with the five books of the Greek Pentateuch 487 lemmas (63%) and uses 48 specific words appearing only in the Deuterocanonical and Apocryphal books of the LXX, which is an aftermath of the normal evolution of the language⁴⁰.

Pre-print version

³⁰ 618 words used only once, 227 only twice, 99 three times, 68 four times. PRYKE, *Redactional style*, 28. Interesting reflection about the exact number of Mark's words in HEAD, «Mark's Vocabulary», 80-83.

³¹ Of Mark's 1,315 lemmas, 2806 types, and 11133 tokens, only 128 lemmas (10%), 819 types (29%), and 1116 tokens (10%) do not overlap with LXX. This means that the distribution of those words is consistent. And these outcomes should be reduced due to the presence of proper names in this comparison with the LXX corpus available.

³² Ἰσκαριώθ, Βεελζεβούλ, Καῖσαρ (4x) and Γολγοθᾶ re also excluded in the statistics.

³³ γερασσηνός, ναζαρηνός, μαγδαληνή, καναναῖος, γαλιλαῖος [Γαλιλαία (1 Kings 9,12)], συροφοινίκισσα [Συρία (2 Sam 8,5) + φοίνικες (Deut 3,9 מִן־תְּיָבִי)]. Ἱεροσολυμίτης appear in Ecclus 50,27 and 4 Macc 4,22; Κυρηναῖος in 2 Macc 2,23 and Ἑλληνίς in 2 Macc 6,8.

³⁴ Ἡρωδιανοί, σαδδουκαῖος and φαρισαῖος. These last two appear in Josephus.

³⁵ τεσσαράκοντα = τεσσαράκοντα (Gen 5,13); τηλαυγῶς = τηλαυγής (Lev 13,24).

³⁶ Five complex words are: εἴωθα (Mark 10,1) appears 4x in LXX. δύνω, to go down in 2 Chron 18,34. κεφαλαῖω, to strike on the head, in Ecclus 32,8. According to EGD σκύλλω and σκύλον could come from the same root.

³⁷ Cfr. Table 6. There are 1900 neologisms in the LXX according to Muraoka's Dictionary (GELS, xiii). Approximately 10%. J. K. AITKEN, «Neologisms: A Septuagint Problem», *Interested Readers. Essays on the Hebrew Bible in Honor of David J. A. Clines* (ed. J. K. AITKEN – C. MAIER – J. CLINES) (Atlanta 2013) 315-329.

³⁸ Of those 34 words identified by Morgenthaler as specific to the LXX, the majority are subsequently attested in the classical or postclassical authors, inscriptions and papyri. MORGENTHALER, *Statistik*, 176.

³⁹ σάββατον is also attested in P.Cair. Zen. 4 59762 (III BCE) and BGU 20 2846 (50 BCE).

⁴⁰ ἀγανακτέω, ἀκυρόω, ἄλας, ἄλυσις, ἀνάκειμαι, ἀνακλίνω, ἀπάτη, ἀπιστία, ἀσέλγεια, ἄφθαρτος, δαπανάω, διαγίνομαι, ἐκθαμβέω, ἐκθαυμάζω, ἑλληνίς, ἐννοχος, εὐκαιρῶς, εὐκοπος, εὐχαριστέω, κατευλογέω, κοινόω, κτίσις, κυρηναῖος, μεθερμηνεύω, νυμφών, ὄψια, πάντοτε, παρασκευή, περίκειμαι, πήρα, ποταπός, πρασιά, προλαμβάνω, πρόσκαιρος, προσμένω, σατανᾶς, σκανδαλίζω, σπεῖρα, σπλαγγίζομαι, στρατιότης, συμβούλιον, συνακολουθέω, συνανάκειμαι, συναποθνήσκω, ὑπόκρισις, φανερός, φάντασμα, φθόνος.

Table 1. 128 Words not in LXX

LEMMA	ATESTATION	ROOT IN LXX
CLASSICAL AND HELLENISTIC WORDS		
ἄσβεστος	Homer, Plato, Josephus, Philo.	ἀ πρίν. + σβεστός Lev 6,2
ἄνιπτος	Homer, Hesiod, Philo.	ἀ πρίν. + νίπτω Gen 18,4
ἀχειροποίητος	Pherecydes (DGE).	ἀ πρίν. + χειροποίητος Lev 26,1
ἄλεκτοροφωνία	Aesop, Strabo.	ἄλεκτωρ + φωνή Prov 30,31 + Gen 29,11
ἀλλαχοῦ	Xenophon, Josephus, Philo.	ἄλλος Gen 19,12
ἀνασεῖω	Thucydides, Xenophon, Plutarch, Josephus, Philo.	ἀνα + σεῖω Judg 5,4
ἄναλος	Aristophanes, Strabo.	ἀνά+ ἄλας (GE) ἄλς, ἄλας Sir 39,26, ἄλς Gen 14,3
ἀνάγαιον	Philo Mechanicus, PSI 709.17 (VI BCE).[ἀνώγαιον in Xenophon. ἀνάγαιον SB 3 7267 (184 BCE). ἀνάγαιος P.Oxy 79]	ἄνω + γαῖα Ex 20,4 + 2 Kings 18,35
ἀποδημέω	Plato, Herodotus, Josephus, Philo.	ἀπό + δῆμος Num 1,20
ἀπόδημος	Plato, Aristotle, Josephus.	ἀπό + δῆμος Num 1,20
ἀποστεγάζω	Aristotle, Empedocles, Strabo, Athenaus.	ἀπό + στεγάζω Ps 103,3
ἀπόστολος (2x)	Demosthenes, Plato, Josephus.	ἀποστέλλω Gen 2,8
ἀσπασμός	Plato, Josephus, Philo, Plutarch [ἀσπάζομαι in Polybius]	ἀσπάζομαι Ex 18,7
γενέσια	Herodotus, Josephus, Plutarch.	γένεσις Gen 2,4
γονυπετέω (2x)	Euripides, Polybius.	γόνυ + πέτομαι Deut 28,35 + Job 20,8
δαμονίζομαι (4x)	Philemon (IV BCE), Josephus, Plutarch. [ἐδδαμονίζοντες P.Herc 1050 (100-1 BCE)]	δαίμων Isa 65,11
διαβλέπω	Plato, Plutarch.	διά + βλέπω Gen 45,12
διακονέω (5x)	Plato, Xenophon, Josephus, Philo.	διακονία 1 Macc 11,58, διάκονος Prov 10,4
δυσκόλως	Xenophon, Isocrates, Josephus, Philo.	δύσκολος Jer 30,2
ἐκπνέω (2x)	Aristotle, Plato, Josephus, Philo, Plutarch.	ἐκ + πνέω Ep. Jer 1,60
ἐκφύω	Homer, Plato, Euripides, Josephus, Philo.	ἐκ + φύω Ex 10,5
ἐμβάπτω	Xenophon, Aristophanes, Athenaeus, III CE.	ἐν + βάπτω Ex 12,22
ἐπιγραφή (2x)	Plato, Thucydides, Isocrates, Josephus, Philo, Plutarch. BGU 6 1443	ἐπί + γραφή Ex 32,16
ἐπίλω	Xenophon, Euripides, Josephus, Philo.	ἐπί + λώω Gen 42,27
ἐπιράπτω	ἐπιράπτω Theophrastus, Galen.	ἐπί + ράπτω Gen 3,7
ἐσχάτως	Xenophon, Aristotle, Polybius, Philo.	ἔσχατος Gen 33,2
ἱματίζω	Plato, Xenophon, Josephus, Thucydides. WL.	ἱμάτιον 1 Macc 11,58
μαθητής (46x)	Plato, Xenophon, Aristotle.	μανθάνω Ex 2,4
μονόφθαλμος	Herodotus, Strabo.	μονο + ὄφθαλμός Ex 21,24
μυρίζω	Isocrates, Plato, Herodotus, Aristotle.	μύρον Ex 30,25
νοννεχῶς	Aristotle, Polybius, Plutarch, Josephus [νοννεχῆς Euripides]	νοῦς + ἔχω Isa 10,7
παρόμοιος	Aristotle, Herod, Xenophon, Thucydides.	παρά + ὅμοιος Job 35,8
πετράδης	Thucydides, Sophocles, Aristotle, Plato, Polybius, Plutarch.	πέτρος + ὄδης, πέτρα Ex 17,6
πιστικός	Plato, Artemidorus Daldianus, II CE.	πίστις Deut 32,20
προαύλιον	Plato, Aristotle, Pollux, II CE.	πρό + αὐλή Ex 27,9
προσαίτης	Isocrates, Xenophon, Aristophanes, Plutarch.	πρός + αἰτέω 2 Macc 7,10
προσκυλίω	Aristophanes, Polyaeus of Macedonia, II CE.	πρός + κυλίω Prov 26,27
προσορμίζω	Aristotle, Demosthenes, Philo.	πρός + ὄρμος Gen 49,13
πυρέσσω	Plato, Aristotle, Josephus.	πυρετός Deut 28,22
πώρωσις	Hippocrates, Galen.	πωρόω Job 17,7
σκύλλω	Aristotle, Xenophon, Herodianus, II CE. P.Oxy 2.295 (35 CE)	σκυλμός 3 Macc 4,6
σταυρός (4x)	Herodotus, Xenophon, Josephus, Philo, Plutarch.	σταυρόω Esther 7,9
συζητέω (6x)	Plato, Epictetus. P.Oxy 1673.20 (II CE).	σύν + ζητέω Gen 19,11
συμπνίγω (2x)	Theophrastus, Aristophanes.	σύν + πνίγω 1 Sam 16,15
σχίσμα	Aristotle, Theophrastus. P.Giss.Univ 4 44 (200-1 BCE). Rufus, II CE.	σχίζω Gen 22,3
σωφρονέω	Plato, Aristotle, Xenophon, Herodotus, Josephus, Philo.	σώφρων 4 Macc 15,10
τελώνης (3x)	Aristotle, Josephus, Plutarch. BGU 6 1259 (100 BCE)	τέλος Gen 46,4
τελώνιον	Posidippus, Strabo. BGU 4 1118 (22 BCE)	τέλος Gen 46,4
θυγάτριον (2x)	Menander, Aristophanes, Epictetus, Demosthenes, Plutarch, Josephus, Xenarch.	dim. θυγάτηρ Gen 5,4
ιχθύδιον	Aristophanes, Chrysippus, Strabo, Plutarch. Lucianus sophist, II CE. O.Claud. 02; P.Oxy 784 (I BCE).	dim. ιχθύς Gen 1,26
κυνάριον (2x)	Plato, Xenophon, Epictetus.	dim. κύων Ex 11,7

ώταριον	Anaxandrides IV BCE. Athenaus. P.Ifao 3.37 (136 BCE). ID 384 (196 BCE), ID 421.54 (II BCE).	dim. ούς Gen 20,8
πλοιάριον	Xenophon, Aristophanes, Strabo. P.Cair.Zen 2.59217 (254 BCE). Menander, III BCE, Pollux, II CE.	dim. πλοῖον Gen 49,13
κράβαττον (5x)	Rhithon, Crito (Pollux). Epictetus. WL. κράβαττος P.Lond 2.191 (117 CE).	root not in LXX
άγαρεύω	Menander, Josephus. WL. Chr.Wilck 439 (42 CE)	root not in LXX
άδημονέω	Plato, Xenophon, Josephus, Philo, Plutarch.	root not in LXX
άρτύω	Homer, Aristotle, Polybius, Josephus, Philo.	root not in LXX
άφρίζω (2x)	Sophocles, Plutarch.	root not in LXX
γαλήνη	Homer, Plato, Aristotle, Josephus, Philo, γάληνός in Polybius.	root not in LXX
κερδαίνω	Aristotle, Plato, Xenophon, Polybius, Josephus, Philo.	root not in LXX
κολλυβιστής	Menander, Lysias. κολλυβιστήριον in P.Teb. 485 (II BCE)	root not in LXX
κυλλός	Hippocrates, Aristophanes.	root not in LXX
πίναξ (2x)	Aristotle, Plato, Herodotus, Polybius.	root not in LXX
πρύμνα	Homer, Aristotle, Polybius, Philo, Plutarch.	root not in LXX
σίναπι	Anaxippus. P.Tebt 1.913 (III BCE). P.Oxy 920.2 (II CE).	root not in LXX
σπόγγος	Homer, Plato, Philo. PSI 535.20 (III BCE).	root not in LXX
σπυρίς (2x)	Aristophanes, Athenaeus, Epictetus, Philo. P.Iand.Zen 53 (257 BCE).	root not in LXX
στιβάς	Herodotus, Xenophon, Polybius, Philo.	root not in LXX
τρίζω	Herodotus, Isocrates. Aristotle, Philostratus. τρισώ Is 38,14 Sym; τρίζησω Am 2,13 Aq.	root not in LXX
χοῖρος (4x)	Plato, Homer, Xenophon, Plutarch. [LXX ὄς Lev. 11,7].	root not in LXX
POSTCLASSICAL WORDS		
άρχισνάγωγος (4x)	Lk. SEG 8.170, SEG 20.442. Dionysius of Halicarnassus.	άρχή + συναγωγή Ex 12,47
άφεδρών	Mt. [άφεδρος Lev 12,2]. WL: BL 12. Dioscorides pharmacologist, I CE. Galen, II CE. SEG 13.521.233 (II BCE).	άπό + έδρα Deut 28,27
βάπτισμα (4x)	Mt, Lk, Rom. Procopius, VI CE	βαπτίζω 2 Kings 5,14
βαπτισμός	Col, Heb. Josephus.	βαπτίζω 2 Kings 5,14
βαπτιστής (2x)	Mt, Lk. Josephus.	βαπτίζω 2 Kings 5,14
γαμίζω	Mt, Lk, 1 Cor. Apollonius Dyscolus, II CE.	γάμος Tob 11,19
διαφημίζω	Mt. Dionysius of Halicarnassus, Josephus.	διά + φημίζω Gen 24,47
έκπερισσώς	Mark	έκ + περισσώς 2 Macc 8,27
ένταφιασμός	John. [ένταφιάζω in Philodemus of Gadara, I BCE and Plutarch].	ένταφιάζω Gen 5,2
έξαντης	Act, Phi. Aratus, III BCE, Polybius, Diodorus Siculus. WL	έξ + ατής
έπισυντρέχω	Mark	έπί + σύν + τρέχω Gen 18,7
εύκαιρέω	Act, 1 Cor. Polybius, Josephus, Plutarch, Philo. P.Cair.Zen 3 59365 (242 BCE)	εύ + καιρός Gen 6,13+ 1 Macc 11,42
κάκειθεν	Josephus. PSI 4 406 (260 BCE). BGU 8 1768 (64 BCE)	crasis for και + έκειθεν Gen 2,10
κατεξουσιάζω	Mt [κατεξουσία IG 14.1047.5]	κατά + έξουσιάζω Eccl 2,19
καυματίζω	Mt. Rev. Epictetus, Plutarch. WL	καῦμα Gen 8,22
κεφαλιώ	Mark. [κεφαλαιώ: Plato, Aristotle, Xenophon]	κεφαλαιώ Sir 32,8; κεφαλή Gen 3,15
κωμόπολις	Strabo.	κόμη + πόλις 2 Macc 14,16 + Gen 10,12
μεταμορφώ	Mt, Rom, 2 Cor. Plutarch, Diodorus Siculus.	μετά+ μορφώ μορφή Judg 8,18
οικοδεσπότης	Mt, Lk. Alexis, Plutarch, Josephus, Epictetus.	οἶκος + δεσπότης Gen 7,1 + Gen 15,2
όνικός	Mt. P.Col.Zen 2.107.4 (III BCE).	όνος Ex 21,33
παιδιόθεν	Mark [Gen 47.3 in Codex Alexandrinus: εκ παιδιοθεν εως του νυν]. Hapax in Bible. P.Lond 5 1731 (585 CE).	παιδιον Gen 17,12
παραλυτικός (5x)	Mt. Rufus, Dioscorides pharmacologist. [παράλυσις and παραλύω in Polybius] P.TM 63131	παράλύω Gen 4,15
προμεριμνάω	Mark	πρό + μεριμνάω Ex 5,9
πρωτοκαθεδρία	Lk	πρώτος + καθέδρα 1 Sam 20,18
πρωτοκλισία	Mt. Lk. SB 6 8993 (175 BCE). ID 1520.33 (153 BCE). πρωτοκλίσιον 2 Macc 4,21.	πρώτος + κλισία 3 Macc 6,31
σμιρνίζω	Dioscorides pharmacologist.	σμίρνα Ex 30,23
στασιαστής	Josephus, Dionysius of Halicarnassus. P.Cair.Zen 3 (226 BCE)	στασιάζω 2 Macc 4,30
συσπαράσσω	Lk. Maximus of Tyre sophist, II CE.	σύν + σπαράσσω 2 Sam 22,8
συσταυρώ	Mt, John, Rom [σταυρώω, to crucify in Polybius]	σύν + σταυρώω Est 7,9
ύπερπερισσώς	Mark	ύπερ + περισσώς 2 Macc 8,27
ύστερησις	Phi	ύστερέω Ecclus 7,34
ψευδόχριστος	Mt	ψευδής + χριστός Lev 4,5

ἄγνωφος	Mt. P.Cair.Zen 92.16 (III BCE).	root not in LXX
οὐά	Epictetus. Dio Cassius.	root not in LXX
κολαφίζω	Mt, 1Cor, 1 Pet. Testamenta of the XII Patriarchs.	root not in LXX
ψυχίον	Mt. ψυχία Plural in Archigenes (II CE). ψιζ Plutarch.	dim. ψιζ root not in LXX
αββα	Gal, Rom	Aramaic
βοανηργές	Mark	Aramaic
γέεννα (3x)	Mt, Lk, Jam	Aramaic. 2 Kings 23,10
έφαθά	Mark	Aramaic
κουμ	Mark	Aramaic
κορβάν	Mark. [Inscription Jebel Hallet Et-Tûri. Mt and Josephus κορβανάς]	Aramaic. Lev 2.1
λεμα	Mt	Aramaic. Ps 22,1
ράββι (3x)	Mt, John. [CIJ 2.1.210 (before 70 CE)]	Aramaic
ράββουεΐ	John. [TADAE B4.3.11]	Aramaic. Dn 4,33
σαβαχθανι	Mt	Aramaic. Ps 22,1
ταλιθα	Mark	Aramaic
ώσαννά (2x)	Mt, John	Aramaic. Ps 118.25
δηνάριον (3x)	Mt, Lk, John, Rev. Epictetus, Plutarch. ChLa 43 1241 (I BCE). CIIP 1/2 1102. CIG 4451.	Latin
κεντυρίων (3x)	Polybius, M 1392, IOGIS 196.9 (I BCE). P.Oslo 2 26.23 (I BCE). SB 5 8427.9 (I BCE).	Latin
κιήνος	Mt. ABSA 12.178 (I BCE). IGRom. 4.1213 (II CE). Papyri. CPR 5 4 R (237 CE).	Latin
κοδράντης	Mt. SEG 55.821. IC 2 11.3	Latin
λεγιών (2x)	Mt, Lk. Plutarch λεγεών. BGU 4 1104.34 (I CE); P.Oxy 2 276.9 (I CE). I.Ephesos 243.6 (I CE).	Latin
μόδιος	Mt, Lk. Polybius, Epictetus, Plutarch. WL. OGIS 533.30 (I BCE).	Latin
ξέστης	Epictetus, Josephus. BGU 16 2669 (5 BCE). IG 7.3498.54 (I BCE).	Latin
πραιτόριον	John. P.Oxy 58.3917 (125 CE). SIG 880.63 (202 CE). Procopius, Pseudo- A rianus.	Latin
σπεκουλάτωρ	P.Mich. 8.469.22 (125 CE). BuEp 1959.260 (II-III CE).	Latin
φραγελλώ	Mark. [φλαγγέλιον in John. P.Lond. 2.191.11 (110 CE)].	Latin

Pre-print version

3.2 Words not appearing in the LXX

Which are these 128 Markan words not appearing in the LXX? What do they reflect? Can they provide us with valuable information to understand the Gospel better? In order to analyse these words, they can be grouped into several sets.

First, of those 128 lemmas that do not appear in the LXX, 85 lemmas are derived or composed from lemmas which do appear in the LXX, as can be checked in Table 1⁴¹, while 43 are clearly not derived or composed from words appearing in the LXX⁴². In fact, these 85 lemmas have meanings close to their roots and could very easily be recognised by the discursive community⁴³ receiving the Gospel. These words are transparent because a Greek native speaker could readily recognize the constituent morphemes. In fact Greek is a rather synthetic language and relative transparent⁴⁴. Of the 128 lemmas not appearing in the LXX, 10 belong to only 6 roots⁴⁵ and *κἀκεῖθεν* is a crasis of an expression appearing in the LXX. Moreover, the roots of the diminutives⁴⁶ found in Mark also appear in the LXX (with the exception of *ψίξ*). Several of these diminutives (forms in *ίον*) had lost their diminutive meaning and replaced the corresponding base nouns⁴⁷. All these considerations effectively reduce the original 128 lemmas not appearing in the LXX to as few as 43, most of which are Latin (10) or Aramaic words (12).

Second, 26 of the 128 lemmas not appearing in the LXX are only found in Mark or the NT (*hapax legomena*), most of them being Latin (2) or Aramaic words (12). Firstly, these *hapax legomena* are very few indeed⁴⁸ and their roots appear both in Septuagint or other texts. Secondly, the Latin and Aramaic loanwords found in the Gospel deserve further comment. Their presence reflects a language contact situation. They have been used more extensively than in other texts of Antiquity. According to Martin Hengel: “There is no document of antiquity like the Gospel of Mark with so much Aramaic and Hebrew present”⁴⁹. There are

⁴¹ The following formations are extremely productive: verbs in *ίζω*, *αζω*, *εω*, *οω*, *εωω* and nouns ended in *ιον*, *μος*, *μα*, *της*, *σις*, *ισσα*. S. COLVIN, *A historical Greek reader*. Mycenaean to the Koiné (Oxford 2007) 68.

⁴² The following are words which roots do not appear in the LXX (except the Latin and Aramaic words): 7 verbs, 2 adjectives, 1 interjection and 13 nouns. The verbs: *ἀγγαρεύω*, *ἀδημονέω*, *ἀρτύω*, *ἀφρίζω*, *κερδαίνω*, *κολαφίζω*, *τρίζω*. Adjectives. *κυλλός*, *ἄγναφος*. Interjection: *οὐά*. Nouns: *γαλήνη*, *τελώνης*, *τελώνιον*, *πίναξ*, *σπυρίς*, *κολλυβιστής*, *πρύμνα*, *πώρασις*, *σίναπι*, *σπόγγος*, *στιβάς*, *χοῖρος*, *ψιχίον*.

⁴³ A discourse community is a group of people who share a set of discourses, understood as basic values and assumptions, and ways of communicating about those goals. They are groups that have goals or purposes, and use communication to achieve these goals. J. SWALES, *Genre analysis*. English in academic and research settings (Cambridge 1990) 21-32.

⁴⁴ M. SILVA, *Biblical words and their meaning*. An introduction to lexical semantics (Grand Rapids, MI 21994) 49.

⁴⁵ *τελώνης* and *τελώνιον*; *ἐκπερισσῶς* and *ὑπερπερισσῶς*; *ἀποδημέω* and *ἀπόδημος*; *βάπτισμα*, *βαπτιστής*, *βαπτισμός* and *ἐμβάπτω*.

⁴⁶ Diminutives in Mark [6, but 5 in LXX]: *θυγάτριον* dim. *θυγάτηρ*, daughter; *ιχθύδιον* dim. *ιχθύς*, fish; *κυνάριον* dim. *κύων*, dog; *ψιχίον* dim. *ψίξ*, crumb; *ωτίριον* dim. *οῖς*, ear; *πλοιάριον* dim. *πλοῖον*, boat. All of these words appear in the LXX unless *ψίξ*. Several of them could have lost their meaning as diminutives. Other diminutives appearing in Mark but also in LXX: *κοράσιον* dim. *κόρη*, girl (Esth 2,7; Tob 6,12). *παιδίον* dim. *παῖς*, child (Gen 17,12). *σανδάλιον* dim. *σάνδαλον*, sandal (Isa 20,2). J. J. K. ELLIOTT, «Nouns with Diminutive Endings in the New Testament», *Novum Testamentum* 12:4 (1970) 391-398. J. M. WATT, «Diminutive Suffixes in the Greek New Testament: A Cross-Linguistic Study», *Biblical Ancient Greek Linguistics* 2 (2014) 29-74.

⁴⁷ S. TORALLAS TOVAR, «Koine, Features of», *EAGLL* 2 2 (ed. G. GIANNAKIS) (Leiden 2014) 273-277, here 276.

⁴⁸ Cfr. SWETE, *Mark*, xlv and HEAD, «Mark's Vocabulary», 95-100.

⁴⁹ M. HENGEL, «Probleme des Markusevangeliums», *Das Evangelium und die Evangelien*. Vorträge vom Tübinger Symposium 1982 (ed. P. STUHLMACHER) (WUNT 28; Tübingen 1983) 221-265, here 243.

ten Latin loanwords (μόδιος, σπεκουλάτωρ, δηνάριον [3x], ξέστης, κήνσος, φραγελλώω, κεντυρίων [3x], κοδράντης, πραιτώριον, λεγιών [2x]) which is a considerable number for a text of the first century⁵⁰. Latin loanwords appearing in Mark have been morphologically and syntactically adapted to the recipient language and had been generally accepted in Koine Greek when Mark wrote his Gospel. On the other hand, there are few Aramaic loanwords⁵¹ in the Gospel (σάββατον, πάσχα, σατανᾶς), all of which appear in the LXX. The remaining eleven Aramaic words⁵² in the Gospel are cases of codeswitching and not loanwords⁵³. The functions of the Latin and Aramaic loanwords are different. The Latin loanwords are not translated, implying that the receiving community could understand them, in fact, two Latin words are used to translate two Greek words (κοδράντης and πραιτώριον). In contrast, the Aramaic switches of code are translated into Greek and have a particular significance in the Gospel, being used as literary devices: Jesus' words when performing miracles (ταλιθα κουμ, εφφαθα); ἀμήν (14x) acting as a discourse marker, the people's acclamation when Jesus entered Jerusalem (ὠσαννά); Jesus' last words on the cross (Ελωι Ελωι λεμα σαβαχθανι); the word Jesus used when talking with God (αββα) and the title by which Jesus' disciples addressed him (ράββί 3x).

Third, 70 lemmas (54%) of the 128 lemmas of Mark not appearing in the LXX, are attested before Aristotle and in the Hellenistic period. This reflects that Mark uses the normal vocabulary of his time which most part goes back before Aristotle. In fact, Markan words coming from the LXX as ἄγγελος (Mk 1,2), ἀγρός (Mk 5,14), σῖτος (Mk 4,28) and τέκτων (Mk 6,6) are found in the oldest written form of Greek, the Mycenaean Greek (the Linear B tablets, XV-XII BCE), and are still used today in Greece, after 3,500 years⁵⁴.

Fourth, the remaining 32 lemmas are only attested in postclassical authors such as Epictetus, Polybius, Josephus, Philo, Plutarch, etc., and in papyri or inscriptions. They reflect the normal evolution of the language, which builds new words constantly. Actually, the greater part of the Greek vocabulary consists of words that are in one way or another the product of word formation. Few words, in fact, consists of just a root⁵⁵.

Fifth, 105 of this 128 words only appear once in Mark. Of the remaining words not appearing in the LXX (excluding the Latin loanwords), the following can be underlined: μαθητής⁵⁶ (46x), διακονέω⁵⁷ (5x) and βάπτισμα (4x, only found only in Christian writers), which are important to Mark's theology. συζητέω (6x) not in LXX appears in classical texts. Other

⁵⁰ E. DICKEY, «Latin influence on the Greek of documentary papyri: An analysis of its chronological distribution», *ZPE* 15 (2003) 249-257.

⁵¹ They would surely be part of the vocabulary of that discursive community.

⁵² Aramaic loanwords and expressions (12) βοανηγές, ταλιθα κουμ, εφφαθα, ράββί (3x), ράββουνεί, κορβᾶν, ὠσαννά (2x), γέεννα, αββα, λεμα σαβαχθανι. ἀμήν (14x, 1 Chr 16,36; Tob 8,8). προσάββατον (Jdt 8,6; Ps 92,1). σάββατον (Ex 16,23). πάσχα (3x, Ex 12,21). Ελωι (Judg 5,5). σατάν (1 Kings 11,14) and σατανᾶς (Sir 21,27).

⁵³ Their functions have been analysed in A. DELGADO GÓMEZ, «Get up! Be opened! Codeswitching and Loanwords in the Gospel of Mark», *JSNT* 42:3 (2020) 1-38.

⁵⁴ C. C. CARAGOUNIS, *The Development of Greek and the New Testament* (WUNT 167; Tübingen 2004) 25-26.

⁵⁵ E. VAN EMDE BOAS – A. RIJKSBARON – L. HUITINK, et al., *Cambridge Grammar of Classical Greek* (Cambridge 2019) 261.

⁵⁶ The noun תַּלְמִיד (disciple), which later in rabbinic linguistic usage plays a great role, in the Hebrew OT it is found only in 1 Chr 25,8 translated in LXX as μανθανόντων. The companion of Moses (Ex 24,13) or of the prophets is not called a disciple, but a תַּלְמִיד (servant), translated as λειτουργός. Elisha is Elijah's servant (ὁ λειτουργός Ελισαιε 2 Kings 6,15). To refer to the servant or disciple the LXX uses ὑπουργός (1x), δοῦλος, λειτουργῶν (8x) and λειτουργός (2x), θεράπων (10x), παῖς, ὑπηρέτης.

⁵⁷ The verbs used in LXX to refer to this concept are λατρεύω (2 Chr 7,19), λειτουργέω (2 Chr 8,14) and δουλεύω (1 Kings 16,31).

words are used to refer to new concepts that emerged at that time: τελώνης (3x) and τελώνιον, σταυρός (4x) and συσταυρόω (although σταυρόω appears in LXX), δαιμονίζομαι (coming from the Hellenistic worldview), ἀρχισυνάγωγος (4x), κράβατος (5x) which Matthew and Luke replaced by κλίνη. χοῖρος substitutes ὄς which is used in LXX. γαμίζω appears in Mark while in LXX συνοικέω (15x) and γαμέω (Est 10,3; 2 Mac 14,25) are used.

Table 2. Lemmas in LXX

Lemmas in LXX: 1113		Lemmas not LXX: 128		
Canon LXX	Apocry LXX	Classical + Hellen	Postclassical	Mark / NT
1065	48	70	32	26

In conclusion, Mark's vocabulary is very closely (90%) related to the books of the LXX. Moreover, as it has been demonstrated this number could be reduced to only 43 lemmas (96.5%) not appearing in the LXX. But his vocabulary is not limited to the LXX, actually it reflects the contact language situation with Latin and Aramaic (22) and the normal evolution of the language (33).

Pre-print version

4 Comparison with other works

In order to understand and value the great presence of LXX's words in Mark's Gospel, in this section, a comparison will be made between the vocabulary of the Septuagint and that of other Greek works. Table 3 compares the number of lemmas (roots) found in several texts written in Koine Greek in a Jewish register to LXX's lemmas. The term "token" refers to the total number of words in a text regardless of how often they are repeated and the term "type" refers to the number of distinct words in a text.

Table 3. Comparison of lemmas from different Jewish books to LXX

	Tokens	Total Lemmas	Lemmas not in LXX	%Lemmas not in LXX
LXX	605,276	13,607		
Mark's Gospel	11,133	1,315	128	10.02%
Paul's auth letters	24,093	2,071	274	13.23%
Joseph and Asenet	8,224	1,403	40	2.85%
Josephus, Antiquities	312,072	11,500	6,218	54.07%
Josephus' Works	473,671	14,198	8,370	58.95%
Philo's Works	437,490	12,725	7,232	56.83%

All of these works listed in Table 3 are written in Koine Greek during the first century CE, in different styles, but they belong to the Jewish–Hellenistic register. Josephus and Philo's vocabularies are much broader than that of the other works and it can be appreciated how separated are their vocabularies from the LXX. On the one hand stand the vocabularies of *Joseph and Aseneth*, Mark and Paul which are very close to the LXX. On the other hand, Philo and Josephus are clearly separated from the LXX's vocabulary reflecting what we know of its Attic and high style. However, this difference is surprising because a greater closeness could be expected given the big number of lemmas of Philo and Josephus' works.

Following, Table 4 compares the number of types and tokens of several works with the vocabulary of the LXX. *Agesilaus* and *Evagoras* were written in Attic or classical Greek (IV BCE) and have been chosen because they are labelled as "ancient biographies" and have been taken as "genre models" for Mark's Gospel by several authors. Among the works which shows a Jewish register stand the works of Mark, Paul, and *Joseph and Aseneth* which were written in Koine Greek close to a low style, while Josephus, Philo, and Polybius are exponents of that Koine Greek that imitates classical Greek⁵⁸. Epictetus' *Discourses* are the prime example of the literary texts which have many points of contact linguistically with the NT⁵⁹ and they have been labelled "as the closest thing we have to a representation of the educated spoken language of the second century CE"⁶⁰. Epictetus' language and the language of the NT are "a reasonably close reflection of the everyday Greek of the majority of the literate population in the early centuries CE, subject, as always, to the influence of the ordinary written language of business and administration learned in school"⁶¹. Philostratus'

⁵⁸ The written variety of Koine Greek included from everyday documents written by the civil service to high literature by writers consciously emulating classical models (Polybius, Strabo, and Plutarch), and the relatively unsophisticated Greek of the New Testament. The highest written register, the standard language (the Classical Attic of the fifth century BCE represented e.g. in Demosthenes), and the lowest spoken registers form the poles of a continuum.

⁵⁹ R. BROWNING, *Medieval and modern Greek* (London 1969) 23.

⁶⁰ G. C. HORROCKS, *Greek. A history of the language and its speakers* (Oxford 2010) 146.

⁶¹ HORROCKS, *Greek*, 147.

Apollonius written in the second century, is an exponent of the second sophistic and the Atticism and Classicism, and is related to the ancient biographical genre.

Table 4. Comparison of words in Classical and Jewish Authors with those in LXX.

	Tokens	Types	Tokens not in LXX	Types not in LXX	% Tokens not in LXX	% Types not in LXX
LXX	605,276	43,779				
Mark's Gospel	11,133	2,806	1,116	819	10.02%	29.19%
Paul's auth letters	24,093	4,920	2,676	1945	11.11%	39.53%
<i>Joseph and Aseneth</i>	8,224	1,930	656	375	7.98%	19.43%
Josephus, <i>Antiquities</i>	312,072	41,345	61,337	29,424	19.65%	71.17%
Josephus' Works	473,671	55,557	96,205	41,588	20.31%	74.86%
Philo's Works	437,490	55,658	98,567	42,371	22.53%	76.13%
Polybius' <i>Histories</i>	299,313	37,514	68,620	28,402	22.93%	75.71%
Epictetus' <i>Discourses</i>	74,992	14,756	14,350	9,144	19.14%	61.97%
Xenophon's <i>Agesilaus</i>	7,378	2,733	1,657	1,279	22.46%	46.80%
Isocrates' <i>Evagoras</i>	4,598	1,750	1,009	760	21.94%	43.43%
Philostratus' <i>Apolloni</i>	82,100	19,202	23,760	13,814	28.94%	71.94%

As has already been stated Mark uses 1,315 lemmas out of 11,133 words. On the most conservative estimate only 128 words do not appear in the LXX, representing 9.73% of the total lemmas. Of the works analysed, Mark's Gospel has the second highest coincidence of vocabulary with that of the LXX.

An analysis of *Joseph and Aseneth* shows unexpected results. It was written in Greek⁶², using 8,224 words (tokens) from 1,042 lemmas including proper and place names, and contains only 40 lemmas that do not appear in the LXX. It is the work with the highest percentage of Septuagintal vocabulary (97.15%). *Joseph and Aseneth* is characterized by the paratactic style and makes use of expressions and complete sentences from the LXX (e.g. καὶ ἐγένετο καὶ αὐτὸ ἰδοὺ) as well as multiple quotations from the Psalms, Genesis, Exodus and Isaiah. There are in total 260 references from LXX⁶³.

Paul's authentic letters⁶⁴ contain a significant presence of Septuagintal vocabulary (86.77% and only 274 lemmas not in LXX⁶⁵) and biblical quotations. My analysis cannot corroborate Riddle's statistics which are as follows: "The non-Septuagint element in the vocabulary of the of the Markan Gospel is 5.7%, and of Paul the average is 6.92%."

Philo and Josephus who wrote in Koine Greek and in a Jewish register, use a wider vocabulary than Mark's (76.13% and 74.86% respectively) and their syntax is more complex than Mark's⁶⁶. Josephus follows Polybius' style whereas Philo follows the style of Plato. The Septuagint also influenced Josephus and Philo, but did not affect their syntax, which was close the Atticistic Greek of the first century. It is particularly striking that Josephus, who in

⁶² E. M. HUMPHREY, *Joseph and Aseneth* (Sheffield 2000) 31.

⁶³ M. PHILONENKO, *Joseph et Aseneth*. Introduction, Texte critique, Traduction, et Notes (Leiden 1968) 31. G. DELLING, «Einwirkungen Der Sprache Der Septuaginta in 'Joseph und Aseneth'», *Journal for the Study of Judaism* 9:1 (1978) 29-56, here 56.

⁶⁴ D. W. RIDDLE, «The Non-Septuagint Element in the Vocabulary of Paul», *JBL* 47:1/2 (1928) 74-90, here 83.

⁶⁵ The number of proper names in the authentic letters is 114 according to my calculation. 274 = 388-114 proper names.

⁶⁶ According to my calculations Mark and Philo have 76% of common lemmas while Josephus and Mark 80%. K. FUGLSETH, «Common Words in the New Testament and Philo: Some Results from a Complete Vocabulary Comparison», *Neotestamentica et Philonica*. Studies in honor of Peder Borgen (ed. P. BORGES – D. E. AUNE – T. SELAND – J. H. ULRICHSEN) (Leiden 2003) 393-414.

his *Antiquities* is telling a similar narrative as in the books of the LXX ⁶⁷, has a greatly improved syntax, style and vocabulary compared with the LXX, as is reflected in the above statistics.

Polybius, the greatest exponent of the literary high level of Koine Greek ⁶⁸ also uses a different vocabulary, very distant from the LXX (75.71%). Only 23 words (of 300,000) appearing in Polybius are Latin loanwords, but according to Dubuisson only πατρίκιος is a received and integrated loanword in Polybius ⁶⁹.

The statistics from Epictetus' *Discourses* are very significant, because sharing a close relationship with Mark in terms of language variety, his vocabulary is far from the LXX (61.97%).

Xenophon's *Agesilaus* and Isocrates' *Evagoras*, two works written in Attic Greek several centuries earlier, show, as would be expected, a greater distance from the vocabulary of the Koine Greek of the LXX (46.8% and 43.43% respectively). Philostratus' *Apollonius*, a clear exponent of the classicism of the second century, also shows a clear distance from LXX's vocabulary (71.94%).

In sum, Mark's vocabulary is very close to LXX's vocabulary and it must be understood as a conscious and personal choice of the author. The coincidence with Paul and *Joseph and Aseneth* in the ratio of words shared with the LXX corroborates this assertion.

Pre-print version

⁶⁷ Josephus claims to offer a completely accurate rendering of the Bible in Greek. T. RAJAK, «Josephus and the Septuagint», *The Oxford handbook of the Septuagint* (ed. A. SALVESEN – T. M. LAW) (Oxford 2021) 421-433, here 424.

⁶⁸ HORROCKS, *Greek*, 96.

⁶⁹ M. DUBUISSON, *Le latin de Polybe*. Les implications historiques d'un cas de bilinguisme (Paris 1985) 55.

5 Mark and the Greek vocabulary of its time

Once Mark's vocabulary has been compared with a corpus as limited as the LXX, it may be interesting to wonder about the relationship of Mark's vocabulary with the snapshot of the Greek vocabulary available to him in the first century CE, as we can access it in others literary texts, inscriptions and papyri (both literary and documentary). This vocabulary of the first century would be the accumulation of words from other periods (e.g. the classical period), adding the new words coming from derivation, compounding and borrowing, and removing the words not in use or forgotten (for example for other dialects).

Although the vocabulary of the Gospel of Mark is essentially the vocabulary of its time, it only represents a very limited part of the language in general use. Thus, the GE dictionary contains 132,884 entries of Greek words ⁷⁰ and LSJ 116,500 of which Mark uses only 1,315 lemmas. Also the LXX represents a very limited range of words, near to 43,700 lemmas.

In this sense it must stressed that although the vocabulary of the Gospel has a significant congruence with that of the LXX, the New Testament and the Septuagint do not constitute a homogeneous corpus from a lexicological point of view ⁷¹. The books of the Septuagint were perceived as part of a canon and belonged to the Jewish and Jewish-Christian discursive communities, but these books were written displaying a small number of registers and literary genres. They show a very limited part of the Greek lexicon of the third and second centuries BCE.

The vocabulary of the Septuagint is not identified with the vocabulary of a discursive community. It could simply represent part of the religious, narrative, poetical and historical registers of the Greek vocabulary of the Jewish community. In fact LXX's Greek is a peculiar Greek, a translation Greek, the aftermath of a literary achievement. Moreover, the Greek Jews of Alexandria belonged to several discursive communities, because they were part of the normal life of their city. In this sense, Philo's texts could represent part of the Jewish vocabulary related to the philosophical register of this community.

All of this leads us to wonder about the nature of Mark's vocabulary. What is it made of? Does Mark's vocabulary reflect an accurate snapshot of the vocabulary of his time or is it an anachronistic language due to its relationship with the LXX? It is important to underline that no one in the first century CE spoke using phrases like *καὶ ἐγένετο*, which would sound strange to someone who did not know the texts of the LXX ⁷². In this sense, we assume that Mark wrote a text that was intended to be understood by his discursive community and his translations of the Aramaic sentences to Greek reflect this aim. Furthermore, his text was well understood and spurred the interest of Matthew and Luke, who, improving their syntax, respected Mark's vocabulary, given that 82% of Matthew's vocabulary and 81% of Luke's is shared with Mark.

As it can be verified in table 5, the result of comparing Mark's vocabulary with the corpus of Greek texts before Aristotle shows that 90.33% (1,129 lemmas) of Mark's vocabulary occurs in classical or pre-Aristotelian Greek. Only 119 lemmas are not found in authors before Aristotle. This confirms and adds weight to the conclusions of the earlier studies of Thayer,

⁷⁰ MONTANARI, *The Brill Dictionary of Ancient Greek*, vii.

⁷¹ WEIGER, «Le Vocabulaire», 450.

⁷² *καὶ ἐγένετο* appears 21x in Philo and 3x in Josephus. *καὶ εὐθύς* not in Josephus and 9x in Philo.

Kennedy, Potwin and Morgenthaler⁷³. According to my calculations, Kennedy, basing his findings on Grimm's lists, asserted that 80% of all of the vocabulary of the NT dated from before 322 BCE⁷⁴ while Potwin⁷⁵ proposed a percentage of 83.76%. This present analysis corrects these findings.

These 119 post classical lemmas, which comprise 9.04% of the Markan vocabulary, appear in the LXX, Polybius, Epictetus, Josephus, Philo, Plutarch, etc., as well as in papyri and inscriptions. They would not have appeared strange to the reader, because they belonged to the normal vocabulary of their time. The presence of these new words reflects the normal changes in the Koine language during the three centuries between the translation of the books of the LXX and the final redaction of Mark's Gospel. According to Browning: "The Koine Greek did not remain static but was in process of continuous development. There were no doubt also local differences within it"⁷⁶.

These postclassical words were derived or compounded from words belonging to the classical period, which could easily be recognized⁷⁷. As Potwin states in his analysis of NT postclassical words: "They are, with very few exceptions, derivatives or compounds, and from roots found in the Greek classics"⁷⁸. The words and their roots, as well as their relationship with the LXX are set out in Table 5.

Table 5. 119 Words not in Classical Authors⁷⁹

LEMMA	LXX	M	ATTESTATION	ROOT IN LXX-
NOT IN LXX				
βοανηργές			Mark	Aramaic
ἐκπερισσός			Mark	περισσός Ps 30,24
ἐπισυντρέχω			Mark. [ἐπιτρέχω in P.Fay 107.7]	ἐπί + σύν + τρέχω Gen 18,7
ἐφραθά			Mark	Aramaic
κουμ			Mark	Aramaic
προμερμνάω			Mark	μερμνάω Ex 5,9
ταλιθα			Mark	Aramaic
ὑπερπερισσός			Mark	περισσός Ps 30,24
κεφαλαίω			Mark. [κεφαλαίω Plato, Aristotle, Xenophon]	κεφαλαίω Sir 32,8
παιδιόθεν			Mark. [Gen 47,3 in Codex A. P.Lond 5 1731 (585 CE)].	παῖς Gen 9,25
αββα			Rom, Gal	Aramaic
γένενα (3x)			Mt, Lk	Aramaic. 2 Kings 23,30
ἐνταφιασμός			John	ἐνταφιάζω Gen 50,2
κατεξουσιάζω			Mt	κατά + ἐξουσιάζω Eccl 2,19
λεμμα			Mt	Aramaic. Ps 22,1
προτοκαθεδρία			Mt, Lk	καθέδρα Ps 1,1
ράββι (3x)			Mt, John [CIJ 2.1.210 (before 70 CE)]	Aramaic
ράββουνεί			John [TADAE B4.3.11]	Aramaic. Dn 4,33
σαβαχθανι			Mt	Aramaic. Ps 22,1

⁷³ L. S. POTWIN, «The New Testament Vocabulary. III. Native Words not Found in Classical Authors», *Bibliotheca Sacra* 37:147 (1880) 503-527. L. S. POTWIN, «The New Testament Vocabulary», *Bibliotheca Sacra* 37:148 (1880) 640-660. THAYER – GRIMM – WILKE, *Lexicon*, 691-699. MORGENTHALER, *Statistik*, 175-176.

⁷⁴ KENNEDY, *Sources*, 62 and 134.

⁷⁵ POTWIN, «The New Testament Vocabulary», 653.

⁷⁶ BROWNING, *Medieval and modern Greek*, 23.

⁷⁷ All this mass of new words we have seen to be derived from the words of the Classical period. They were not obscure in origin. POTWIN, «The New Testament Vocabulary», 658.

⁷⁸ POTWIN, «The New Testament Vocabulary», 653.

⁷⁹ The third column in this table signifies with an asterisk (*) the words identified as LXX neologisms in GELS, e.g. not attested before the LXX, but this identification was carried out following LSJ, and must be corrected (X).

συσταυρόω	Mt, John, Rom, Gal. [σταυρόω, to crucify in Polybius].	σταυρόω Est 7,9
ύστερησις	Phi. [ύστερημα Judg 18,10]	ύστερέω Num 9,7
φραγγελλόω	Mt. [φλαγγέλλιον in P.Lond. 2.191.11 (110 CE) and John]	Latin
ψευδόχριστος	Mt	ψευδής + χριστός Lev 4,5
ώσαννά (2x)	Mt, John	Aramaic. Ps 118,25
άγναφος	P.Cair.Zen 92.16 (III BCE)	root not in LXX
άφεδρόν	WL; BL 12. SEG 13.521.233 (II BCE). Galen.	έδρα Deut 28,27
άρχισυνάγωγος	SEG 8.170; SEG 20 442	συναγωγή Ex 12,47
βάπτισμα (4x)	[Procopius, VI, CE]	βαπτίζω 2 Kings 5,14
βαπτισμός	Josephus.	βαπτίζω 2 Kings 5,14
βαπτιστής (2x)	Josephus.	βαπτίζω 2 Kings 5,14
γαμίζω	Apollonius Dyscolus, II CE.	γάμος Tob 11,19
δηνάριον (3x)	Epictetus, Plutarch. ChLa 43 1241 (I BCE). CIIP 1/2 1102. CIG 4451.	Latin
διαφημίζω	Dionysius of Halicarnassus, Josephus	διά + φημίζω Gen 24,47
εύκαιρέω	Polybius, Josephus, Plutarch, Philo Psi 4 374 (250 BCE) Demetrius to Zenon. WL.	εὖ + καιρός Gen 6,13 + 1 Macc 11,42
κάκειθεν	Josephus. PSI 4 406 (260 BCE). BGU 8 1768 (64 BCE).	crasis for καί + έκειθεν Gen 2,10
καυματίζω	Epictetus, Plutarch, WL	καῦμα Gen 8,22
κεντυρίων (3x)	Polybius, M 1392, IOGIS 196.9 (I BCE). P.Oslo 2 26.23 (I BCE). SB 5 8427.9 (I BCE).	Latin
κῆνσος	ABSA 12.178 (I BCE). IGRom. 4.1213 (II CE). CPR 5 4 R (237 CE).	Latin
κοδράντης	SEG 55.821. IC 2 11.3.	Latin
κολαφίζω	Testamenta of the XII Patriarchs. Mt, Paul, 1 Pet.	root not in LXX
κορβάν	Mt and Josephus κορβανάς	Aramaic
κομόπολις	Strabo.	κόμη + πόλις 2 Macc 14,16 + Gen 10,12
λεγιών (2x)	Plutarch λεγεών. BGU 4 1104.34 (I CE); P.Oxy 2 276.9 (I CE). I.Ephesos 243.6 (I CE). Mt, Lk.	Latin
μεταμορφώω	Plutarch, Longinus, Diodorus Siculus	μετά + μορφή. μορφή Judg 8,18
μόδιος	Polybius, Epictetus, Plutarch. WL. OGIS 533.30 (I BCE). Mt, Lk.	Latin
νουνηχός	Polybius, Josephus, Plutarch	νοῦς + έχω (Isa 10,7)
ξέστης	Epictetus, Josephus. BGU 16 2669 (5 BCE). IG 7.3498.54 (I BCE).	Latin
οικοδεσπότης	Epictetus, Josephus, Plutarch.	οἶκος + δεσπότης Gen 7,1 + Gen 15,2
όνικός	P.Col.Zen. 2 107 4 (III BCE)	όνος Gen 12,16
ουά	Epictetus, Dio Cassius	Interjection
παραλυτικός (5x)	Dioscorides pharmacologist, I CE, Rufus medical writer, II CE.	παραλύω Gen 4,15
πραιτόριον	P.Oxy 58.3917 (125 CE). SIG 880.63 (202 CE). Procopius, Pseudo-Arrianus. John.	Latin
πρωτοκλισία	SB 6 8993 (175 BCE). ID 1520.33 (153 BCE). πρωτοκλίσιον 2 Macc 4,21.	πρῶτος + κλισία 3 Macc 6,31
σπεκουλάτωρ	P.Mich. 8 469 22 (125 CE). BuEp 1959 260 (II-III CE).	Latin
σμυρνίζω	Dioscorides pharmacologist	σμυρνίζω, σμύρνα Ex 30,23
στασιαστής	Josephus, Dionysius of Halicarnassus, P.Cair.Zen 3.59484.4 (226 BCE)	στασιάζω 2 Macc 4,30
συσπαράσσω	Maximus of Tyre sophist, II CE	σύν + σπαράσσω 2 Sam 22,8
ψυχίον	ψυχία Plural in Archigenes (II CE)	dim. ψιξ
SEPTUGINTAL WORDS		
άθετέω (2x)	Ex 21,8 - Sept. Epictetus, Polybius, Josephus, Plutarch	άθετος, τίθημι
άκυρόω	1 Esd 6,31 - Sept. Josephus, Plutarch	ά + κυρόω, κύρος
άποκεφαλιζώ (2x)	Ps 151,7 - Sept. Atheneus, Arrianus, II CE, Epictetus	άπό + κεφαλιζώ
άποκυλίω (2x)	Gen 29,3 - Sept. Diodorus Siculus, Lucian	άπο + κυλίω
γαζοφυλάκιον	2 Kings 23,11 - Sept. Diodorus Siculus, Josephus, OGI 225.16 (III BCE). Strabo	γάζα + φυλακή
διασκορπίζω	Num 10,35 - Sept. Polybius, Josephus	διά + σκορπίζω
έκθαμβέω (4x)	Ecclus 30,9 - Sept. Polybius, Orph.A. 1218	έκ + θαμβέω, θάμβος
έκθαμάζω	Ecclus 27,23 - Sept. Dionysius of Halicarnassus, Josephus, Longinus	έκ + θαυμάζω

ἐναγκαλιζομαι	Prov 6,10	-	Sept. Meleager I BCE, Plutarch	ἐν + ἀγκαλιζομαι, ἀναγκάζω ἀνάγκη
ἐνδιόσκω	2 Sam 1,24	*	Sept. Josephus. ἐνδιόσκόμενος SIG 2857.13	ἐν + δύω
ἐξάπινα	Lev 21,4	*	Sept. SB 7792 and SEG 8.595. P.Giss 68.6 (II CE). ἐξάπινης Menander	ἐξάπινης
ἐξομολογέω	Gen 29,36	-	Sept. Josephus, Strabo, Plutarch	ἐξ + ομολογέω
ἐξουδενέω	2 Kings 19,21	*	Sept. ἐξουδενόω 1 Sam 15,23. PSB 7524.8 (II BCE). ἐξουθενέω Josephus. ἐξουδενίζω in Plutarch	ἐξουδενίζω, ἐξ + οὐδέεις
ἐπαύριον	Gen 19,34	-	Sept. Polybius	ἐπι + αύριον
ἐπίβλημα	Isa 3,22	-	Sept. Plutarch, Galen	ἐπί + βλημα, βάλλω
ἐπισυνάγω	Gen 6,16	-	Sept. Polybius, Josephus, Longinus	ἐπί + συνάγω
ἐρήμισις	Lev 26,34	-	Sept. Josephus, Euripides	ἔρημος
εἰκοπος	Gen 35,2	-	Sept. Polybius, Plutarch, Diodorus Siculus	εὔ + κοπος
καθαρίζω (4x)	Ex 29,36	-	Sept. Josephus	καθαρισμός
καθαρισμός	Ex 29,36	-	Sept. P.Mich. 3.185.16, P.Lond. 2.168.11 (II CE)	καθαρίζω
κατακυριεύω	Gen 1,28	-	Sept. Diodorus Siculus	κατά + κυριεύω, κύριος
κατάλυμα	Ex 4,24	-	Sept. Polybius	κατά + λῦμα
καταπέτασμα	Ex 26,31	*	Sept. Josephus	καταπετάννιμι, κατά + πετάννιμι
κατέναντι	Gen 2,14	-	Sept. Lucian	κατα + ἐναντι, ἐν + αντι
κατευλογέω	Tob 10,14	-	Sept. Plutarch	κατά + εὔ + λογέω
κοράσιον (5x)	Ruth 2,8	-	Sept. Plutarch	dim. κόρη Deut 32,10
μακρόθεν (5x)	Gen 21,16	-	Sept. Polybius	μακρός
μεγιστάν	2 Chr 26,18	-	Sept. Josephus	μέγας
μεθερμηνεύω	Sir 1,30	-	Sept. Polybius, Strabo, Josephus, Plutarch	μετά + ἐρμηνεύω
μογύλαος	Isa 35,6	-	Sept. Claudius Ptolemy mathematician, II CE	μόγις + λαλέω
μύλος	Ex 11,5	-	Sept. Strabo, Plutarch, Diodorus Siculus, Athenaus	μύλη
νάρδος	Cant 1,12	-	Sept. Strabo, Plutarch	Possible loanword
νυμφόν	Tob 6,4	-	Sept. Heliodorus novelist, III–IV CE, Pausanias, II CE	νύμφη
όλοκαύτωμα	Ex 10,25	*	Sept. Josephus	όλοκαυστος, όλος + καυστός καίω
παράπτωμα	Ps 18,13	-	Sept. Polybius	παρά-πτομα
πάσχα (4x)	Ex 12,21	*	Sept. Josephus, Philo, Athenaeus	Aramaic
περίσσευμα	Eccl 2,15	-	Sept. Plutarch	περισσός, περί
προσεγγίζω	Gen 3,6	-	Sept. Polybius, Diodorus Siculus	ἐξ + αὐτῆς
προσευχή	2 Sam 7,27	*	Sept. Josephus, Philo	πρός + εὐχομαι
πρόσκαιρος	4 Macc 15,2	X	Sept. Josephus, Strabo, Plutarch	πρός + καιρος
σάββατον (11x)	Ex 16,23	*	Sept. BGU 20.2846 (50 BCE); P.Cair.Zen. 4.59762.6 (III BCE)	Aramaic
σκανδαλίζω (8x)	Sir 9,5	-	Sept. P.Oxy 2407.5.43 (III CE)	σκάνδαλον
σκοτιζω	Ps 68,24	-	Sept. Dionysius of Halicarnassus, Plutarch	σκότος
συλλαλέω	Ex 34,35	-	Sept. Polybius, Strabo, Plutarch	συν + λαλέω
συμβούλιον (2x)	4 Macc 17,17	-	Sept. Josephus, Plutarch	συμβάλλω
συνανάκειμαι	3 Macc 5,39	*	Sept. Diodorus Siculus. Strabo	συν + ανά + κειμαι
τρυμαλιά	Judg 6,2	*	Sept. Plutarch	τρῦμα, τρύω
ὕποληνιον	Isa 16,10	*	Sept. Pollux, II CE	ὕπο + λήνιον
ψευδοπροφήτης	Jer 6,13	*	Sept. Josephus, Philo	ψευδο + προφήτης
ἀμήν (14x)	1 Chr 16,6	X	Sept	Aramaic
ἀναθεματίζω	3 Macc 5,39	*	Sept	ἀνάθεμα, ἀνατίθημι
βδέλυγμα	Dan 12,11	*	Sept	βδελύσσω Ex 5,21
ελωι	Judg 5,5	X	Sept	Aramaic
ἐντάλμα	Isa 29,13	-	Sept	ἐντολή
εὐλογητός	Gen 12,2	*	Sept	εὔ + λόγος
μοιχαλῖς	Prov 18,22	*	Sept	μοιχός
οὐαί (2x)	Num 21,29	*	Sept	Interjection
πειρασμός	Ex 17,7	*	Sept	πειράζω, πειρά
προσάββατον	Ps 92,1	*	Sept	πρός + σάββατον
σατανᾶς (5x)	Sir 21,27	*	Sept	Aramaic
σκληροκαρδία (2x)	Deut 10,16	*	Sept	σκληρός + καρδία

Of these 119 post-Aristotelian lemmas, 61 appear in the LXX whereas 58 do not. Of these 58 lemmas, 34 are exclusively post-Aristotelian and do not appear in the LXX (G4), while 24 are exclusive to Mark or the NT and are not attested in others sources (G3).

Mark contains 48 lemmas which are found in the LXX and are also attested only in post-classical authors (G2). That is to say, they are words found universally in Koine Greek and are not specific to the LXX. The 35 postclassical words which appear in the LXX are almost all derived or composed from words that were in use previously in classical Greek.

Table 6. Post-Aristotelian Words

Postaristotelian Words: 119			
LXX: 61		Not LXX: 58	
G1. Only LXX and not attested in postclassical authors	G2. LXX and Postclassical	G3. Only NT or Mark	G4. Only Post
13	48	24	34

The 34 Markan lemmas which are exclusively post-Aristotelian (G4) are attested in a number of authors from the Koine epoch such as Polybius, Plutarch, Josephus, etc., as well as in papyri and inscriptions⁸⁰. Their presence reflects the normal changes expected in the language⁸¹. They are also derived or compounded from words of the classical period.

In Mark there are only 24 lemmas not attested in other authors (G3, except NT writers), papyri or inscriptions or only in a very late attestation. These words are few and almost all coincide with the Latin loanwords and Aramaic switches of code. The exceptions are: ἐκπερισσῶς, ἐνταφιασμός, ἐπισυντρέγω, κατεξουσιάζω (Mt), κεφαλίω, παιδιόθεν, προμερινάω, πρωτοκαθεδρία (Mt, Lk), συσταυρόω (Mt, John, Rom), ὑπερπερισσῶς, ὑστέρησις and ψευδόχριστος.

All Markan *hapax legomena* in the NT appear in the classical or postclassical authors except: ἐξουθενέω, καταβαρύνω, παιδιόθεν, προσάββατον which appear in the LXX, but not in the rest of the NT.

In sum, most of Mark's vocabulary is both classical and Septuagintal (1,067 lemmas, 85.98%) which confirms the close relationship between the LXX and classical Greek⁸². The more recent discoveries of papyri and inscriptions confirm this connection⁸³. The words not appearing both in classical Greek or in the LXX are words derived or compounded from roots that are found in the classical Greek and in the LXX. According to Marguerite Harl: "There are almost no words in the LXX which the reader could not easily understand from a root

⁸⁰ "It is a mistake to regard inscriptions and papyri uniformly as witnesses to vernacular or popular Greek". J. A. L. LEE, «The Vocabulary of the Septuagint and Documentary Evidence», *Die Sprache der Septuaginta/The Language of the Septuagint* (ed. E. BONS – J. JOOSTEN) (LXX.H 3; Gütersloh 2016) 98-108, here 102.

⁸¹ Morgenthaler's statistic (column II) is wrong in many cases. MORGENTHALER, *Statistik*, 175-176.

⁸² "La grande masse du vocabulaire de la LXX appartient à la langue grecque classique." M. HARL, «La langue de la Septante», *La Bible grecque des Septante. Du judaïsme hellénistique au christianisme ancien* (ed. G. DORIVAL – M. HARL – O. MUNNICH) (Paris 1988) 223-266, here 243.

⁸³ Montevicchi insists on the correspondence between the lexicon of papyri and that of the LXX. O. MONTEVECCHI, «La lingua dei papiri e quella della versione dei LXX: due realtà che si illuminano a vicenda», *AnScR* 1 (1996) 71-80.

known to them. The vocabulary of the LXX is not ‘barbaric.’ Its language is properly Greek”⁸⁴.

This analysis confirms that the vocabulary of Mark belongs to the normal Greek of its time⁸⁵. Only 10 lemmas in Mark are not attested in the Greek language⁸⁶ (included Latin and Aramaic words) which confirms Deissmann’s conclusion from one hundred years ago that “the list of words considered ‘peculiar’ to the New Testament and/or the LXX has been steadily reduced so that less than one percent of the vocabulary of the entire New Testament is yet without parallel”⁸⁷. According to G. H. R. Horsley, the Septuagint translators and the NT authors wrote in the language of their time, without inventing words or giving new meanings to old words in order to express their ideas⁸⁸.

Nonetheless, the convergence of Mark and LXX’s vocabularies is far from coincidental. Even those words used in Mark that are not found in the LXX, are not far removed from it. Several of these words have roots which appear in the LXX and are close in meaning to them. On the other hand, the use of words not appearing in the LXX and especially the use of loanwords, even though not neologisms, reflects the author’s freedom as a writer.

Pre-print version

⁸⁴ HARL, «La langue», 247. “The bulk of the Pentateuch vocabulary is the same as that of contemporary Greek”. J. A. L. LEE, *A lexical study of the Septuagint version of the Pentateuch* (Chico, CA 1983) 146.

⁸⁵ “Le vocabulaire du Nouveau Testament est-il le même que celui du monde méditerranéen hellénophone du I^{er} siècle après Jésus-Christ.” WEIGER, «Le Vocabulaire», 440.

⁸⁶ Cicero frequently employs in his letters Greek words which do not occur elsewhere, yet which, from his use of them, we may infer were tolerably familiar. ABBOTT, *Essays*, 87.

⁸⁷ A. DEISSMANN, *Light from the ancient East*. The New Testament illustrated by recently discovered texts of the Graeco-Roman world (London 1910) 78.

⁸⁸ G. H. R. HORSLEY, «Divergent Views on the Nature of the Greek of the Bible», *Biblica* 65:3 (1984) 393-403, here 398-399.

6 Conclusion

Several conclusions regarding the vocabulary of the Gospel of Mark can be drawn from this analysis.

First, Mark's vocabulary is closely related (90 %) to that of the Septuagint. The Markan words not found in the LXX (128) are almost all compound or derivate words from roots appearing in the LXX. This number could be reduced to as few as 43 words which roots do not appear in the LXX.

Second, Mark's vocabulary belongs to that of first century Koine Greek. Only six words (excluding the Aramaic and Latin words) are only attested in Mark (*Markan hapax legomena*): ἐκπερισσῶς, ἐπισυντρέχω, κεφαλῖω, παιδιόθεν, προμεριμνάω and ὑπερπερισσῶς. Moreover, 90% of the Markan words are attested before Aristotle and the remaining 119 post-Aristotelian words are also to be found in the vocabulary of several authors writing in a high style (Polybius, Josephus, Philo, etc.). This confirms previous studies which conclude that the Greek of the LXX and the NT are representative of the Greek of their time. The Greek words in the Gospel which do not appear in classical Greek or in the Septuagint are all derivatives or compound words from well-known roots. These words illustrate the flexibility of the Greek language in generating new words as well as the natural evolution of the language.

The exceptions to these previous assertions are the unexpected Aramaic words and switches of code from Aramaic to Greek that appear in the Gospel, together with the Latin words found in it. Although the Greek language was reluctant to accept loanwords, Mark's usage is reflective of the contact language situation that existed between Greek and Latin in the first century and which resulted in the acceptance of several of these loanwords by a number of Greek authors, papyri and inscriptions. With the exception of the Aramaic words present, this reflects the evolution of the Greek language in the first century. The Aramaic switches of code could be a sign of his multilingualism and it must be stressed that these Aramaic sentences and words and their translations have been used to develop sociolinguistic, literary and narrative functions.

Third, the comparison of Mark's vocabulary with the vocabulary of other works reveals part of the intention and style of their authors. On the one hand, Josephus and Philo wrote in a high style, with almost no loanwords, and their vocabularies are not particularly related to the Septuagint (sharing the same ratio of coincidence with the Septuagint as Polybius, Epictetus, Philostratus, Xenophon or Isocrates). A special mention deserves Josephus' *Antiquities*, because although in this work he rewrites several narratives of the LXX covering similar material and was written with a similar register to the Gospel, nevertheless his vocabulary, style and genre differ from that of the Gospel with a much wider vocabulary not so restricted to the LXX's vocabulary. Polybius and Epictetus writing in Koine Greek also show a wider range of vocabulary than Mark not so restricted to the LXX's vocabulary. On the other hand, Mark, Paul and *Joseph and Aseneth* show a clear connection with the Septuagint in terms of style, vocabulary and intertextuality.

In sum, Mark's vocabulary reflects a strong connection with the LXX, but also other elements (expressions, idioms characters, world of the text, quotations, etc.) link Mark's story with the books of the LXX, indicating that it was a clear intention of the author to connect his narrative

with that of the books of the Septuagint which becomes an important tool in interpreting and understanding the Gospel.

Pre-print version